

HIGHER ORDER ASYMPTOTIC SOLUTION FOR WAVE PROPAGATION IN ELASTIC LAYERED COMPOSITES

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Wave propagation normal to the layering of a semi-infinite elastic composite which occupies the space $x \geq 0$ is studied. Each unit cell of the composite consists of two layers of linear, not necessarily isotropic, elastic materials. The stress response at the N -cell distance from $x=0$ due to a unit step stress applied at $x=0$ is obtained by an asymptotic analysis. By comparing the one-term, two-term and three-term asymptotic solutions, we obtain the values of N for which each asymptotic solution may be regarded as a reasonable approximate solution. Finally, we apply the three-term asymptotic solution to $N=5$ and compare the result with the exact solution obtained by the ray theory in the literature. Good agreement is obtained even for this small value of N .

INTRODUCTION

Consider a semi-infinite periodic layered composite as shown in Fig. 1 in which each period 2ω consists of two layers of homogeneous linear elastic materials. The thicknesses of individual layers are $2h_i$ ($i=1,2$) where the subscripts 1 and 2 refer to materials 1 and 2, respectively. We will consider plane wave propagation in the direction x which is normal to the layers. For the problem considered here, the surface $x=0$ need not be the central surface of the first layer. However, we will assume, without loss of generality, that the first layer in which $x=0$ is located is occupied by material 1.

The composite is initially at rest and, at time $t=0$, a uniformly distributed normal stress which is a unit Heaviside step function in time t is applied at the surface $x=0$. We assume that the material property is such that the only displacement generated is in the x -direction. Therefore, the individual layer of the composite does not have to be an isotropic material. The material can be orthotropic with one of the axes of symmetry lying on the x -axis.

Instead of the unit normal stress applied at $x=0$, one can also consider a unit shear stress applied at $x=0$. We then assume that the material property is such that only the transverse displacement is generated.

The asymptotic solution for the above problem for a large distance x has been obtained in [1-3]. However, there seems to be no assurance on the accuracy of the asymptotic solution for a given distance x . In other words, there seems to be no assurance as to how large the distance x should be in order to consider the asymptotic solution as a reasonable approximation.

This paper is an attempt to answer the above question. The solution obtained in [1,2] contains one-term asymptotic solution. In this paper, we obtain two- and three-term asymptotic solutions. By studying the effects of dropping the higher order terms, we obtain an estimate on the value of x for which the lower-order asymptotic solution may be considered as a reasonable approximation.

Fig. 1 Geometry of the elastic composite

SOLUTION FOR $x = 2\omega N$

The equations of motion and the continuity of the displacements are given by

$$\frac{\partial \sigma_i}{\partial x} = \rho_i \dot{v}_i, \quad (i = 1, 2) \quad (1)$$

$$\frac{\partial v_i}{\partial x} = \dot{\epsilon}_i, \quad (i = 1, 2) \quad (2)$$

where σ_i , ϵ_i , v_i , ρ_i ($i = 1, 2$) are the normal stress, normal strain, normal particle velocity and mass density, respectively. A dot stands for differentiation with respect to time t . The initial and boundary conditions are

$$\left. \begin{aligned} \sigma_i(x, 0) = v_i(x, 0) = \epsilon_i(x, 0) = 0 \\ \sigma_i(\infty, t) = 0 \quad \sigma_1(0, t) = H(t) \end{aligned} \right\} \quad (3)$$

where $H(t)$ is the Heaviside unit step function. The stress-strain relation is

$$\sigma_i = E_i \epsilon_i, \quad (i = 1, 2) \quad (4)$$

where E_i is the material constant.

Let $\bar{f}(p)$ be the Laplace transform of $f(t)$:

$$\bar{f}(p) = \int_0^{\infty} f(t) e^{-pt} dt \quad (5)$$

Equations (1-4) then reduce to

$$\left. \begin{aligned} \frac{\partial^2 \bar{\sigma}_i}{\partial x^2} = k_i^2 \bar{\sigma}_i \\ \bar{\sigma}_i(\infty, p) = 0, \quad \bar{\sigma}_1(0, p) = \frac{1}{p} \end{aligned} \right\} \quad (6)$$

where

$$k_i = p/c_i, \quad c_i = \sqrt{E_i/\rho_i} \quad (i = 1, 2) \quad (7)$$

Since k_i is periodic in x with periodicity 2ω , by using the Floquet theory [4] the solution at $x = 2\omega N$ where N is an arbitrary positive integer is

$$\bar{\sigma}_1(x, p) = \frac{1}{p} e^{-\kappa x} \quad (8)$$

where κ is the characteristic exponent given by (see [2,4,5])

$$\cosh(2\omega\kappa) = \theta \cosh \left[2p\omega \left(\frac{n_1}{c_1} + \frac{n_2}{c_2} \right) \right] - (\theta - 1) \cosh \left[2p\omega \left(\frac{n_1}{c_1} - \frac{n_2}{c_2} \right) \right], \quad (9)$$

$$\theta = \frac{(\rho_1 c_1 + \rho_2 c_2)^2}{4\rho_1 c_1 \rho_2 c_2}, \quad n_i = \frac{h_i}{\omega} \quad (10)$$

The solution at $x = 2\omega N$ is obtained by the inverse Laplace transform;

$$\sigma(x, t) = \frac{1}{2\pi i} \int_{Br} \frac{1}{p} e^{pt - \kappa x} dp \quad (11)$$

where the subscript 1 of σ is omitted here and in the sequel.

Investigation of Eq. (11) in which κ is given by Eq. (9) shows that $p = 0$ is a singular point as well as a saddle point. For small p , κ is linearly proportional to p :

$$\kappa \approx p/c_\infty, \quad (12)$$

where

$$\left. \begin{aligned} \frac{1}{c_\infty^2} &= (\rho_1 n_1 + \rho_2 n_2) \left(\frac{n_1}{E_1} + \frac{n_2}{E_2} \right) \\ &= \left(\frac{n_1}{c_1} + \frac{n_2}{c_2} \right)^2 + 4(\theta - 1) \frac{n_1 n_2}{c_1 c_2} \\ &= \left(\frac{n_1}{c_1} - \frac{n_2}{c_2} \right)^2 + 4\theta \frac{n_1 n_2}{c_1 c_2} \end{aligned} \right\} \quad (13)$$

c_∞ can be identified as the speed of the main pulse in the layered medium [2,3,5]. We will assume that c_∞ is finite and non-zero.

Noticing that $x = 2\omega N$, we rewrite Eq. (11) as

$$\sigma(x, t) = \frac{1}{2\pi i} \int_{Br} \frac{1}{s} e^{t's + 2N\psi(s)} ds \quad (14)$$

where

$$s = p\omega/c_\infty, \quad t' = (c_\infty t/\omega) - 2N, \quad \psi(s) = s - \omega\kappa. \quad (15)$$

Thus, N and t' can be regarded as the non-dimensional distance and time, respectively. We are interested in the solution for large N . We will show in the next section that the stress σ depends on, in addition to N and t' , two parameters which are related to the properties of the composite and its geometry.

THE COMPOSITE PARAMETERS m AND Δ

Let

$$\left. \begin{aligned} m &= \frac{\theta - 1}{\theta} = \frac{(\rho_1 c_1 - \rho_2 c_2)^2}{(\rho_1 c_1 + \rho_2 c_2)^2} \\ \Delta &= 4\theta c_\infty^2 \frac{n_1 n_2}{c_1 c_2} = \frac{4(\rho_1 n_1)(\rho_2 n_2)(\rho_1 c_1 + \rho_2 c_2)^2}{(\rho_1 n_1 + \rho_2 n_2)[\rho_1 n_1 (\rho_2 c_2)^2 + \rho_2 n_2 (\rho_1 c_1)^2]} \end{aligned} \right\} \quad (16)$$

It follows from Eqs. (13) and (16) that

$$\left. \begin{aligned} 1-\Delta &= c_{\infty}^2 \left(\frac{n_1}{c_1} - \frac{n_2}{c_2} \right)^2 \\ 1-m\Delta &= c_{\infty}^2 \left(\frac{n_1}{c_1} + \frac{n_2}{c_2} \right)^2 \end{aligned} \right\} \quad (17)$$

Since the right-hand sides of Eqs. (16) and (17) are positive, we have

$$0 \leq m \leq 1, \quad 0 \leq \Delta \leq 1 \quad (18)$$

It is seen that m represents the impedance "mismatch." m vanishes when the impedances of materials 1 and 2 are identical and assumes the value of unity when the mismatch is the greatest. Δ has no physical interpretation. However, Δ vanishes when either n_1 or n_2 vanishes, i.e., one of the layers has zero thickness. On the other hand, $\Delta=1$ when $n_1/c_1 = n_2/c_2$, which means that the transit times in layer 1 and layer 2 are identical.

Equation (9) can now be rewritten as

$$\cosh(2\omega\kappa) = \frac{1}{1-m} \cosh(2s\sqrt{1-m\Delta}) - \frac{m}{1-m} \cosh(2s\sqrt{1-\Delta}) \quad (19)$$

where s is related to p through Eq. (15). Therefore $\omega\kappa$, a function of s , depends on the two parameters m and Δ introduced in Eq. (16). Consequently, $\psi(s)$ of Eq. (15) also depends on m and Δ . Similarly, the stress σ as given by Eq. (14) depends on these two parameters only. Thus instead of the material properties E_1, E_2 , the mass densities ρ_1, ρ_2 and the thicknesses h_1, h_2 , all we need is the two composite parameters m and Δ .

It follows from Eq. (19) that

$$\omega\kappa = s, \quad \text{when} \quad m = 0 \quad \text{or} \quad \Delta = 0. \quad (20)$$

Equation (14) then yields the trivial solution

$$\sigma(x,t) = H(t'), \quad \text{when} \quad m\Delta = 0. \quad (21)$$

In the remainder of the paper we assume that $m\Delta \neq 0$.

ASYMPTOTIC SOLUTIONS

For small s , let

$$\omega\kappa = s - \frac{\beta_1}{2} \left(\frac{1}{3} s^3 - \beta_2 s^5 + \beta_3 s^7 - \dots \right) \quad (22)$$

where the coefficients $\beta_1, \beta_2, \beta_3, \dots$ can be determined by expanding both sides of Eq. (19) into power series in s and comparing the terms of equal powers. Omitting the lengthy algebra, one obtains

$$\left. \begin{aligned} \beta_1 &= m\Delta^2 \\ \beta_2 &= \frac{2}{45} \left(2 + q - \frac{5}{8} \beta_1 \right) \\ \beta_3 &= \frac{1}{315} \left\{ \frac{16}{3} (2+q) + q^2 + \beta_1 \left(6 - \frac{7}{3} q + \frac{35}{24} \beta_1 \right) \right\} \end{aligned} \right\} \quad (23)$$

where

$$q = (1+m)\Delta \tag{24}$$

It can be shown that β_1 , β_2 and β_3 are all positive for all possible values of $0 \leq m$, $\Delta \leq 1$.

We see from Eq. (23) that β_1 , β_2 and β_3 are expressed in terms of $m\Delta^2$ and q . In fact, one can show that β_j for $j \geq 3$ also can be expressed in terms of $m\Delta^2$ and q only. Consequently, instead of m and Δ one could use $m\Delta^2$ and q as the composite parameters.

Use of Eq. (22) in Eq. (15) and then in Eq. (14) yields

$$\sigma(x,t) = \frac{1}{2\pi i} \int_{Br} \frac{1}{z} e^{\tau z + \frac{1}{3} z^3 - \zeta_2 z^5 + \zeta_3 z^7 - \dots} dz \tag{25}$$

where

$$\left. \begin{aligned} \tau &= \left(\frac{c_\infty}{\omega} t - 2N \right) / (N\beta_1)^{1/3} \\ \zeta_2 &= \beta_2 / (N\beta_1)^{2/3} \\ \zeta_3 &= \beta_3 / (N\beta_1)^{4/3} \end{aligned} \right\} \tag{26}$$

Notice that since $x = 2\omega N$ and the thickness of each unit cell is 2ω , N represents the number of cells between the position x and the impact end. Thus the larger the value of N , the fewer terms are needed in Eq. (25).

ONE-TERM ASYMPTOTIC SOLUTION

When N is so large that ζ_2 and ζ_3 can be ignored, Eq. (25) reduces to

$$\left. \begin{aligned} \sigma(x,t) &= \frac{1}{2\pi i} \int_{Br} \frac{1}{z} e^{\tau z + \frac{1}{3} z^3} dz \\ &= \frac{1}{3} + \int_0^\tau A_1(-s) ds \end{aligned} \right\} \tag{27}$$

where

$$A_1(s) = \frac{1}{\pi} \int_0^\infty \cos\left(sr + \frac{1}{3} r^3\right) dr \tag{28}$$

is the Airy function. Equation (27) was obtained in [1,2].

TWO- AND THREE-TERM ASYMPTOTIC SOLUTIONS

When N is not large enough, the term containing ζ_2 as well as the term containing ζ_3 may not be ignored. The solution of Eq. (25) with ζ_2 , but not ζ_3 , included will be called the two-term asymptotic solution. The solution with both ζ_2 and ζ_3 terms included will be called the three-term asymptotic solution.

Fig.2 Bromwich contour

Fig. 3 Dependence of R on m and Δ

Regardless of two-term or three-term asymptotic solution, Eq. (25) is integrated numerically by taking the Bromwich contour shown in Fig. 2. We have

$$\sigma = \frac{3}{7} + \frac{1}{\pi} \int_0^{\infty} \frac{1}{r} e^{\tau r^3 \cos(3\phi) - A} \sin B r dr \quad (29)$$

$$\left. \begin{aligned} \phi &= \pi/7 \\ A &= \frac{1}{3} r^3 \cos(2\phi) + \zeta_2 r^5 \cos\phi + \zeta_3 r^7 \\ B &= \tau r \sin(3\phi) - \frac{r^3}{3} \sin(2\phi) - \zeta_2 r^5 \sin\phi \end{aligned} \right\} \quad (30)$$

The reasons for choosing the angle $3\pi/7$ in Fig. 2 are to ensure that all terms in A are positive and to eliminate the higher order term r^7 in B. The appearance of r^7 term in B would cause the integrand to oscillate rapidly at large r.

From Eqs. (26) and (23), ζ_2 and ζ_3 depend on N, m and Δ . Thus ζ_2 and ζ_3 are independent parameters. However, it is seen that the ratio

$$R = \zeta_3 / \zeta_2^2 = \beta_3 / \beta_2^2 \quad (31)$$

is independent of N. Moreover, for all values of $0 \leq m, \Delta \leq 1$, it is found that R assumes a very narrow range of values (see Fig. 3),

$$3.04 \leq R \leq 4.28 \quad (32)$$

By letting

$$\zeta_3 = R \zeta_2^2 \quad (33)$$

in Eq. (30), it was found that the numerical integration for σ shows no difference whether one uses $R = 3.04, 3.6$ or 4.28 . Consequently, we will use $R = 3.6$ in the following discussion and hence use

$$\zeta_3 = 3.6 \zeta_2^2 \quad (34)$$

whenever three-term asymptotic solution is needed.

VALIDITY OF ASYMPTOTIC SOLUTIONS

We integrate Eq. (29) numerically. Notice that because of the term e^{-A} in the integrand, the integrand diminishes rapidly. Thus the infinite integral may be replaced by a finite integral.

For one-term asymptotic solutions, we let $\zeta_2 = \zeta_3 = 0$ in Eq. (30) and we reproduced the result given by Eq. (27).

For two-term asymptotic solution we let $\zeta_3 = 0$; while for three-term asymptotic solution we assume ζ_3 to be given by Eq. (34).

In Fig. 4, we show the results for $\zeta_2 = 2 \times 10^{-3}$. We see that the difference between the two-term and three-term asymptotic solutions is not visible. As to the difference between the one-term and two-term asymptotic solution, even though the difference is visible one may consider the difference as an acceptable error in ignoring the ζ_2 term. If this is the case, then we may say that the one-term

Fig. 4 Asymptotic solutions for $\zeta_2 = 0.002$

Fig. 5 Asymptotic solutions for $\zeta_2 = 0.01$

asymptotic solution is a reasonable approximation when $\zeta_2 \leq 2 \times 10^{-3}$. In view of Eq. (26), this implies that the one-term asymptotic solution is a reasonable approximation when

$$N \geq \left(\frac{10^3}{2} \beta_2 \right)^{3/2} / \beta_1 \quad (35)$$

In Fig. 5 we show the results for $\zeta_2 = 10^{-2}$. Here the one-term asymptotic solution is clearly inadequate. On the other hand, the two-term and three-term asymptotic solutions differ very little. If we consider the difference as an acceptable error in neglecting the ζ_3 term, we may say that the two-term asymptotic solution is a reasonable approximation when $\zeta_2 \geq 10^{-2}$. This implies, by Eq. (26),

$$N \geq (10^2 \beta_2)^{3/2} / \beta_1 \quad (36)$$

To illustrate what values of N one obtains from Eqs. (35) and (36), we use the composite whose physical variables are as follows:

$$\left. \begin{array}{ll} \rho_1 = 7.9 \text{ gm/cm}^3 & \rho_2 = 1.15 \text{ gm/cm}^3 \\ E_1 = 12.58 \times 10^{11} \text{ dynes/cm}^2 & E_2 = 0.89 \times 10^{11} \text{ dynes/cm}^2 \\ h_1 = 0.0125 \text{ cm} & h_2 = 0.0392 \text{ cm} \end{array} \right\} \quad (37)$$

This example is taken from [3] and was used in [5]. For this example, Eqs. (16) and (23) give

$$\left. \begin{array}{lll} \Delta = 0.815, & m = 0.665 & \\ \beta_1 = 0.4416, & \beta_2 = 0.1369, & \beta_3 = 0.06755 \end{array} \right\} \quad (38)$$

and Eqs. (35) and (36) give $N \geq 1282$ and $N \geq 115$, respectively. Therefore, for the composite given by Eq. (37), the one-term asymptotic solution is acceptable for points whose distance from $x=0$ is larger than 1282 cells while the two-term asymptotic solution is acceptable for points whose distance is larger than 115 cells.

To establish the reasonableness of the three-term asymptotic solution, we may compare the solution with the four-term asymptotic solution.

DISCUSSION AND CONCLUSION

Equation (35), which gives the minimum number of cells beyond which the one-term asymptotic solution is acceptable, is based on the comparison between the one-term and two-term asymptotic solutions, Fig. 4. If one demands a higher accuracy, then one should use a smaller value of ζ_2 and, consequently, the factor $10^3/2$ in Eq. (35) will become larger. On the other hand, if one can tolerate a larger error, a larger value of ζ_2 can be used and the factor $10^3/2$ may be replaced by a smaller value.

Similar arguments apply to Eq. (36) which gives the minimum number of cells beyond which the two-term asymptotic solution is acceptable.

In [5], the exact solution of the stress response at 5-cell distance from the loading boundary for the composite given by Eq. (37) was obtained by using the ray theory. This means that $N=5$ and, by Eqs. (38) and (26), $\zeta_2 = 0.08075$ and $\zeta_3 = 0.1716$. The value of ζ_2 for this example is larger than the ζ_2 used in Figs. 4 and 5. We use this new value of ζ_2 and ζ_3 in Eq. (30) to obtain the

Fig. 6 Exact and asymptotic solutions at $N=5$

asymptotic solutions and compare the results with the exact solution in Fig. 6. As expected, the one-term and two-term asymptotic solutions do not agree well with the exact solution. The three-term asymptotic solution, for which the range of validity is not established here, agrees reasonably well with the exact solution. Notice that $N=5$ is hardly a large number. Therefore, the asymptotic solutions are not expected to predict well the exact solution. Nevertheless, the three-term asymptotic solution agrees reasonably well with the exact solution, at least for the first peak and the first valley. In [5,6], a theory is proposed by which the stress response can be predicted accurately for points which are as close as one-cell distance to the impact end, i.e., for $N=1$.

It should be pointed out that the largest stress which occurs at the first peak decreases as more terms are included in the asymptotic solution. This implies that the peak stress increases as the distance travelled by the wave increases. As the distance approaches infinite, the peak stress approaches the value 1.273 which is the peak stress of the one-term asymptotic solution.

Finally, one could extend the present analysis to viscoelastic layered composites. A study of the effects of dispersion, dissipation and the distance travelled by the waves in layered composites of general viscoelastic materials was given in [7], although no attempt was made there to predict the accuracy of the solution for a given N .

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